

Analysis of the financial risk management approach of the selected commercial banks in China

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Abstract

With the reform of the overall financial environment and the promotion of the market system, the development of many banks in China has made great progress and great changes. In recent years, China's commercial banks have experienced a variety of measures, such as joint-stock reform, financial restructuring, and so on, and the overall operating pressure has been released accordingly. In the face of increasingly fierce market competition, commercial banks have upgraded their business ideas from a single focus on business scale to a dual focus on business scale and quality. Although we have made great achievements on the road, we cannot ignore the fact that diversified financial risks still exist. Whether from the perspective of practice or academia, the financial risk management of commercial banks has generally received the focus of attention. Based on the cited literature, this paper elaborates on the current situation of the operation and financial risk management of commercial banks in China. Starting from the basic data of many domestic commercial banks, we focused on the analysis of their management status in combination with their business types. We further explored all aspects of the financial risk management of commercial banks by focusing on assets, liabilities, profits and losses, non-performing loans, overdue loans, and banking assessment indicators. We also summarized different evaluation systems and models and analyzed and summarized the advantages and disadvantages of each item.

Keywords: Commercial bank; Structural system; Financial risk.

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Introduction

With the continuous development of China's commercial banks, their financial risk management issues have been of great importance. Under the influence of the global financial crisis, commercial banks are facing more serious risks and crises. Improving the overall risk management ability of commercial banks through the implementation of effective financial risk management to achieve the healthy and long-term development of commercial banks has become an important issue of concern to the entire financial sector in China (Li, 2020). This paper mainly analyzes the problems existing in the financial risk management of commercial banks in China at present and puts forward corresponding countermeasures and suggestions on this basis, so as to comprehensively improve the financial risk management ability of commercial banks and then realize the healthy and orderly development of China's financial industry. With the reform of the overall financial environment and the promotion of the market system, the operation and management systems of many banks in China have made considerable progress. In recent years, through shareholding reform, financial restructuring, and other measures, the overall operating pressure of various commercial banks in China has been eased accordingly. In the face of increasingly fierce market competition, commercial banks have upgraded their business ideas from a single focus on business scale to

a dual focus on business scale and quality. Based on internal and external factors, there are still many hidden risks in the operation and development of China's commercial banks. For example, if the debtor who has used bank credit is unwilling or unable to repay the corresponding debt according to the established contract, the bank will suffer from the risk of credit loss. At present, the overall financial system in the world is developing rapidly. In view of the characteristic mode of separate operation in China, the market risk is more prominent. Many existing problems expose defects in the internal overall process of banks under the current management mode. At the same time, there is also the capital risk that the corresponding liabilities and sudden losses cannot be filled when due.

The overall state of financial risk management largely affects the basic links in the daily operation of commercial banks. Therefore, commercial banks will have to pay attention to financial risk management, and taking corresponding targeted measures is an inevitable choice to achieve stable operation from their own center. With the marketization of interest rates, China's economic environment is constantly improving its degree of openness, which requires commercial banks to pay more attention to financial risk management in a complex and volatile competitive environment. In view of the fact that the financial risk of commercial banks runs through all processes of the bank's operation, it has an impact on the bank's asset profit and loss that cannot be ignored. Therefore, in the face of market transformation and more fierce competition, the management of financial risk has become a top priority for China's commercial banks.

Financial risk management has always been the focus of domestic and foreign scholars. Based on the academic field, commercial banks, as special individuals, are also an important part of the research field of financial risk management. Therefore, the research on financial risk management in commercial banks not only depends on their own development but also needs relevant theories to promote commercial banks to improve relevant systems and apply them to their daily operations.

The credit business is the core business of banking and financial institutions, and the high risks brought by it are inevitable. Therefore, the level of financial risk management is directly related to whether commercial banks can continue to operate steadily, whether they can maintain the stability of their own assets, and even guide the overall market confidence and the direction of the domestic economy. The 19th National Congress and the report put forward for the first time that the banking industry is facing a new round of industrial transformation by implementing the new development concept and strengthening the construction of a modern economic system. During this period, the financial risk management environment has become increasingly complex. A good grasp of financial risks will help commercial banks seize opportunities, stand out in the new environment, and better increase product innovation.

VanHoose (2007) pointed out in his research that commercial bank regulatory indicators focusing on the New Basel Accord have been formed, and all countries have included them in regulatory documents as necessary requirements. The regulatory authorities' control over commercial banks largely depends on the regulatory policies and the actual economic system. In view of the differences in national conditions, scholars and practitioners can hardly reach the same view on determining the specific capital and risk status of commercial banks. At the same time, the actual operational efficiency of commercial banks also has a significant impact on capital and risk conditions. VanHoose (2007) also believes that the combination of efficiency and the actual operation of commercial banks deserves further research. Fiordelisi et al.'s (2013) research focuses on the reputation risk of the banking industry. Its innovation lies in the extension of the types of inherent risks of commercial banks. Through its related demonstration, it shows that the current reputation risk has reached a negative correlation with the specific capital structure and size of commercial banks. Therefore, in the specific study of the financial risk of commercial banks, we should not ignore its importance and should focus on its importance.

Diamond and Rajan (2001) studied the overall liquidity of the industry and concluded that financial risk exists in banks because of the vulnerability of their operations: financial assets, as the core part of assets in the overall operation of commercial banks, replaced the position of fixed assets, and financial liabilities also replaced net assets as the core position of liabilities in the overall operation of commercial banks; the

terms of loans and relevant systems affect liquidity; there are also influencing factors in the same industry; and the grade demand of relevant contracts in different economic periods also affects liquidity.

Mwangi (2012) selected the target case to determine the overall value of the commercial bank, which is negatively related to the financial risk formed in the operation. Based on the actual financial risks of various types of commercial banks in 44 different countries and regions, Mwangi called for the promotion of the overall value of commercial banks to rely on commercial banks to avoid financial risks in the business process more reasonably and effectively.

The discovery, judgment, evaluation, and prevention of financial risks by commercial banks depend on the control and management of all processes in their overall operation (Bessis, 2015; Ojo, 2010). The research model of factor allocation is helpful for commercial banks to better adjust their own business conditions and effectively deal with the occurrence of risks when responding to the reasonable supervision of the regulatory authorities. It is mainly based on the three-pillar research perspectives on the financial risk of commercial banks based on the New Basel Capital Accord.

From the perspective of industry ethics, Hughes et al. (2001) believed that the increase in overall operating income brought about by high risks was bound to be a choice for many commercial banks when their operating efficiency was low, which alleviated some of the deficiencies in the daily development of commercial banks. Relatively speaking, commercial banks with a high proportion of liabilities, based on the management of the regulatory authorities, are the ones that operate better in most cases. The actual efficiency of commercial banks' working capital needs to be studied by judging the overall risk. The size of financial risk largely determines the decision-making mode of commercial banks' operation and management, and the number of risks also reflects the overall efficiency of decision-makers in the operation and management process. The research shows that the overall risk of commercial banks is usually positively related to their overall asset quality. Based on the research of commercial banks in many countries, the overall risk of commercial banks affects the overall asset quality, and financial risk orientation is the factor that western regulators generally use to determine the asset quality of commercial banks.

Gu and Jiang (2016) pointed out that commercial banks currently have more independent interest rate pricing methods and more active overall pricing. With the introduction of the general policy of interest rate reduction and reserve ratio reduction, the Central Bank officially cancelled the setting of the upper limit on the floating rate of deposit interest of financial institutions led by commercial banks in October 2015. After more than ten years of interest rate control, the first liberalization reflects the progress of marketization. In this inheritance, China's commercial banks have not only brought greater business opportunities but also raised the requirements for the overall working capital, which has intensified the changes in interest rates under the overall market environment. In view of the particularity of each process link in the operation of commercial banks, currency is the core foundation of each link, and the operation of funds has brought unstable factors into the overall operation. At the same time, all financial activities in the operation of commercial banks depend on the currency capital process in each operation link. It can be seen that the control of financial risk requires commercial banks to maintain awareness of their own financial risk management and control at all times in the operation process.

Xue (2020) mentioned the analysis of the overall business environment of China's commercial banks. The degree of government intervention has gradually weakened, and interest rate and reserve ratio cuts will undoubtedly endure the most of the impact, causing potential risks. The unreasonable capital structure has increased the probability of risks in the operation of China's commercial banks. At present, the capital adequacy ratio of many large commercial banks in the United States and Japan is about 15%. Many listed banks in China's commercial banks find it difficult to reach this level. The overall structure of financial risk management lacks a complete system, and non-performing loans are increasingly exposed and growing. While reducing the overall operational liquidity, it also delayed the further popularization and realization of the financial risk management model, which lacked systematicity and effectiveness.

The competition among commercial banks also brought about the birth of financial risk. Avoiding financial risk and then controlling it has become an unavoidable topic for commercial banks to achieve stable operations. How commercial banks treat financial risk in a reasonable way among their various business-influencing factors determines the extent of their financial risk control.

Zhang (2013) analyzed the financial risk management of commercial banks in China and said that financial risks exist all the time. How to effectively resist and prevent them is the focus of research on commercial banks to improve their operational models and improve their operational efficiency, which runs through the whole process of the overall operation of the banking industry. Integrating into the market competition in the changing environment and managing the financial risk model reasonably and effectively can help commercial banks further increase their operating income and market share. In the daily operation of commercial banks, there are usually various and changeable factors that determine the uncertainty of their financial risk. Similarly, in the actual operation, there will be errors between the predicted operating income and the final profit, and the overall operating situation will also have additional losses and changes in profit income.

Dai (2015) stated that all commercial banks are actively using various means and measures to compete for customer resources and market share, which leads to the continuous rise of various risks that commercial banks deal with in order, which is also the reason for the increasing financial risk. The inherent market share is constantly divided, and the existing resources of commercial banks are constantly integrated, so the financial risks in their operation will also become more diversified and varied.

With the constant strengthening of the trend of economic globalization, the global financial markets are more closely connected. As one of the important development goals of commercial banks, financial risk management has a very important impact on their development. Strengthening the financial risk management ability of commercial banks will help to enhance the overall risk management ability of commercial banks, enhance their overall competitiveness, and promote the smooth reform of China's commerce. From the current situation of financial risk management of commercial banks in China, there are still many problems, mainly the financial risk management measures need to be improved, the lack of professional financial risk management personnel, and the lack of support and guidance of relevant policies, which have caused potential risks for commercial banks to a large extent, causing many adverse effects on their development. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive and effective analysis of its existing problems, formulate and implement targeted countermeasures and suggestions, so as to comprehensively improve the financial risk management ability of commercial banks, and then promote the healthy development of commercial banks.

For different national conditions and different systems, the crisis caused by the financial risk of commercial banks also has diverse characteristics. Li (2015) explained that based on the general environment of the market economy system, the credit risk and mismatched information brought by the system itself affect commercial banks, so it is significant to have targeted financial risk early warning in the management model adopted. The control of credit risk should be at its initial stage. However, based on the importance of commercial banks to finance, the government has always provided unconditional support, making commercial banks give priority to businesses with high returns, which leads to high risks, and to some extent, the depositors have been abandoned. At the same time, the deposit interest will fall even lower under the control of the supervision, thus reducing the compensation pressure brought by commercial banks in the face of massive deposit taking in bankruptcy.

Financial risks appear in the various daily operations and management links of commercial banks. In view of the financial risks of grassroots operations, Liang et al. (2020) pointed out that there are deficiencies in the cost matching method of grassroots expansion of commercial banks, overall cost scheduling, and product-linked marketing costs, such as decentralized management, multi-directional allocation, and other issues. The financial risk management at the grassroots level is relatively weak. From the perspective of the overall operating trend of the system, the weakness is an ongoing problem. There

may be deviations in the implementation of disciplines and relevant regulations. The requirements for financial personnel are relatively loose, and there is no specific and detailed management model. The use of funds is also arbitrary and lacks planning. The management department practitioners' understanding of the overall financial risk needs to be improved, and further training and education are needed.

It can be seen from the numerous literatures selected that there are many theoretical methods for the research on the financial risk of commercial banks by domestic and foreign scholars after decades of development. For how to reasonably study the financial risks in commercial banks, foreign scholars start with building appropriate risk early warning models and complete the construction of the corresponding evaluation system all the way. Due to the early start, there has been a more mature theoretical system for studying specific risk early warning models abroad, and the financial risk evaluation system is more mature than the domestic status quo, with a large number of excellent achievements. It mainly focuses on the quantitative financial risk early warning model. However, the quantitative financial risk early warning model is based on continuous and complete statistical data and a large number of bankrupt bank samples, which has high requirements for basic data statistics. Foreign theorists rely on a large number of real data sets from commercial banks, including many samples of bankrupt banks, so they can conduct detailed and in-depth research.

As far as the research of many domestic scholars is concerned, it is unavoidable that the research on the financial risk of commercial banks in China started later than that in foreign countries, and the basis of many studies depends on the development of foreign theories. The operational efficiency and overall structure of commercial banks are the first choices for domestic research. In view of the lack of sample data on the bankruptcy of commercial banks in China and the difficulty in obtaining historical data on the financial risk assessment of commercial banks, it is difficult to compare the amount of data when specifically analyzing financial risks with foreign countries.

For the specific research on financial risk in commercial banks, the risk early warning model and the risk evaluation system are two main aspects (Du et al., 2021). After decades of progress, univariate statistical analysis has progressed to multivariate statistical analysis, and multivariate statistical analysis has gradually become the mainstream of risk early warning model establishment. At present, there are many methods in the financial risk evaluation system, such as the DuPont analysis system, the camel analysis system, the balanced scorecard, and the Economic Value Added (EVA) system. In order to better combine financial risk research with real cases of commercial banks, whether it is the Logit model, fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method, entropy value weighting method, Z model, factor analysis method, or biological method—an artificial neural network—all from their respective perspectives, improve the accuracy of relevant predictions in the system.

Due to the particularity of commercial banks, financial risk is in a very important position for them. In this regard, domestic and foreign scholars have paid full attention to the research and application of relevant theories in practice. With the continuous progress and opening of China's banking industry, it is of great significance to further study the financial risks of commercial banks and use effective models to obtain a reasonable evaluation system.

In this paper, the financial risk of commercial banks is the basic research direction. Through analyzing the problems existing in the detection, identification, management, and prevention of financial risks of the commercial banks of the Agricultural Bank of China, we propose to establish a targeted financial risk identification and evaluation model, further improve its overall management methods, and improve internal control systems. Finally, it gives some measures on how to strengthen the existing financial risk management ability of commercial banks.

Current Situation of Financial Risk of China's Commercial Banks

According to the definition of China's Commercial Bank Law, a commercial bank is an enterprise legal person established in accordance with this law and the Company Law of the People's Republic of China to absorb public deposits, issue loans, and handle settlement business. The financial environment at home and abroad is becoming increasingly integrated. China's commercial banks have grown from scratch, from a few to many. Foreign banks are also landing in succession. To sum up, there are already about five or six large commercial banks, more than ten medium-sized commercial banks, and more than one hundred small commercial banks in China. Apart from foreign banks, the competition among them is very fierce.

With the gradual improvement of China's overall financial system and the gradual improvement of the degree of marketization, the development of China's banking industry has made considerable progress in the past decade. In view of the particularity of commercial banks and their impact on the national economy, the regulatory authorities have taken relatively strict supervision over them, which is the root cause of the fact that commercial banks' business operations and risk management are greatly affected by changes in regulatory policies. Based on the specific forms of fund receipt and payment, borrowing, and lending, the financial risks formed in the process of fund operation in China's commercial banks also have corresponding amounts.

The adequacy of liquidity is one of the core objectives of a bank's sound operation. From a macro point of view, the time effect mismatch between assets and liabilities, a large number of short-term investments in long-term loans are widespread, and liquidity risk is becoming increasingly prominent. In view of the control over the liquidity problem of commercial banks during the Spring Festival in 2018, the Central Bank implemented the Community Reinvestment Act (CRA), thus ensuring the liquidity of the entire banking industry. The following points exist in the liquidity problem:

1. The asset composition is single, and the liquidity is weak. Loans account for the majority of the overall structure.
2. The quality of credit assets is difficult to guarantee, resulting in deviation of liquidity.
3. The proportion of liquidity liabilities continued to rise, increasing the potential risks of commercial banks.

At the same time, China's commercial banks are less able to control the total amount of enterprise loans based on liquidity demand. Nominally, as a working capital loan, most of them are in a fixed state, and the liquidity can be seen in general. With the development of the times, the transformation of China's economic system, the constant adjustment of deposit and loan interest rates, and the increasingly open trend, commercial banks are facing the possibility of financial risks caused by interest rate changes. If the interest rate is completely market-oriented, its fluctuation will be more frequent, and the range will be relatively larger.

China's current interest rate is still controlled by the central bank, and banks can only make small self-adjustments on the basis of the interest rate set by the central bank. Therefore, if the deposit and loan interest margin increases and interest rate control is relaxed, the bank's operating profits will inevitably increase. On the contrary, if the deposit and loan interest margin decreases, interest rate control will be further tightened. Although it is conducive to controlling the overall market risk, it will inevitably reduce operating profit, which will increase the difficulty for commercial banks to resist sudden financial risks to a certain extent.

The increasingly fierce competition in the banking industry has increased the operating difficulty of commercial banks, forcing them to continue to expand their businesses and improve themselves. This creates operational risks due to personnel, internal processes, and external business issues. The operational risks caused by personnel include dereliction of duty, violations, and internal fraud. All kinds of violations

and ultra vires contain serious risks, which not only affect employees but also bring loss of commercial reputation and working capital to commercial banks.

The operational risks in the internal processes, such as errors in the information transmission process and the overall operating efficiency, are mainly due to the imperfect system. Usually, it will not be easily found in short-term financial measurement, but it is bound to bring huge financial risks to the operation of commercial banks after repeated operations.

In the actual operation process of commercial bank business, false guarantees are an unavoidable topic. In order to illegally obtain loan funds, some enterprises use false guarantee companies to guarantee, blindly expand guarantee objects, and illegally draw registered capital. Once there is a serious guaranteed circle problem, commercial banks can hardly contain their financial risks, let alone resolve them.

After long-term development, the intermediate business of commercial banks in China has gradually shown the following characteristics: first, the settlement intermediate business grew. The People's Bank of China has continuously strengthened the progress of the electronic process of the overall banking industry, and there is a trend of joint settlement of local and foreign currencies in China, which further increases the proportion of intermediary business in the overall commercial bank income and has a significant impact.

Second, the financial card instrument medium has developed rapidly. The increasing demand of the public for financial services has promoted the upgrading of the overall financial hardware tools of commercial banks. The development of the bank card business has virtually driven the settlement volume of card transactions and has also driven new profit growth points for commercial banks. Third, agency intermediary business innovation is frequent. According to the growing demand for financial services from the public, finance is based on continuous innovation in business, such as agency fees for public utilities. It not only broadens its business scope but also adds new profit points. It is also a way to expand the popularity of commercial banks and obtain a good social response. Fourth, the intermediary business of consulting services is sprouting. Since the mid-1980s, paid information consulting services have developed rapidly, especially the credit evaluation business, which has become another strategic direction for commercial banks to expand their business. In the 1990s, the intermediate businesses such as credit evaluation, information consulting, and asset evaluation became more diversified, forming a more systematic and standardized information consulting business. Fifth, trading intermediary business is rampant. Financial futures, forward foreign exchange contracts, swaps, and options are increasingly widely used.

From the perspective of the five-level loan classification, non-performing loans include concern, subordination, suspicion, and loss. Generally, doubtful loans should be compressed until they exit. However, some commercial banks still classify some non-performing loans as concerning and do not pay enough attention to potential non-performing loan risks. The existence of false interests receivable, industrial investment, mortgage assets, and other factors has caused real losses to China's commercial banks. Although some losses have not been counted in the published financial statements, these hidden non-performing loans have always affected the physical operation of commercial banks as potential financial risks.

Important Problems in Financial Risk Management of Commercial Banks

Financial risk management measures need to be improved

The financial risk management of commercial banks involves the development of their businesses, which is highly complex and has many influencing factors. Therefore, the requirements for risk management methods and measures are high. At present, China's commercial banks' financial risk management and its various methods and measures remain at a lower level. On the one hand, many bank

managers regard financial risk management as the special work of the financial department and do not pay enough attention to it. They do not make necessary innovations in management methods and concepts in their daily work. The traditional financial management methods have been difficult to meet the needs of the current commercial bank business expansion. On the other hand, most commercial banks in China do not pay attention to learning from the experience of large commercial banks at home and abroad in the process of financial risk management, and there is still a big gap between the management methods and models of transnational commercial banks, which makes it difficult to effectively improve their financial risk management capabilities, causing a great negative impact on their development.

Financial risks appear in all aspects of the daily operation of commercial banks and are difficult to avoid. With the gradual deepening of financial markets and the rapid development of financial institutions, financial risks also increase. During the Asian financial crisis in 1998, most commercial banks ended up in bankruptcy due to the credit crisis caused by capital liquidity risk (Wang, 1999). With the macroeconomic diseconomies and even shrinking, the number of bad debts of commercial banks continues to rise with the decline of corporate profits, the increase of loans but the weakening of repayment capacity, and the sharp decline of capital liquidity. The possibility of “running” commercial banks has greatly increased. The only outcome for commercial banks that cannot be merged and restructured is bankruptcy. This situation has occurred in the Korean banking industry, where the number of banks in the overall banking industry has decreased precipitously (Kim, 2017). It can be seen from this that effective diversification of loan risk can be one of the ways for commercial banks to resist the changes in the macro environment. By promoting the diversification of financial products and continuously innovating financial derivatives, the potential financial risks of commercial banks can be more reasonably and effectively dispersed. In Accounting Standards for Enterprises No. 37, Presentation of Financial Instruments, according to Article 36, an enterprise shall classify financial instruments according to their stickers and the nature of relevant information and fully disclose information related to the risks of financial instruments; in Article 43, an enterprise shall disclose the reasons and other considerations for drawing some conclusions about the failure to truly reflect the fair value changes of the relevant financial instruments caused by the quoted risks.

Lack of specialized financial risk management

Talented financial risk management is highly professional and needs to be promoted by professionals. China’s commercial banks are still short of professional financial risk management talents. Although the overall educational level of commercial bank practitioners is constantly improving, their professional financial risk management skills still need to be improved. First, many commercial banks do not pay attention to the comprehensive training of their internal financial risk management personnel in the process of development, and their financial risk management methods and skills are relatively backward, which makes it difficult to strengthen the financial risk management ability by improving the comprehensive quality of internal personnel and fails to effectively play the role of professionals. Secondly, because the overall profitability of China’s commercial banks has a declining trend, most commercial banks have not introduced specialized financial risk management talents from outside, and externally advanced ideas and methods have not effectively flowed into the banks, making it difficult to effectively improve the effect of financial risk management in a short time.

The implementation of the new standards has greatly improved the disclosure of financial instrument risk information in the annual reports of commercial banks, correspondingly reduced the user’s decision-making errors caused by information asymmetry, and improved the ability of information to help users conduct risk analysis. However, the credit criteria do not pay enough attention to the risk distribution, so few commercial banks are willing to disclose the risk distribution on their own, thus misleading the information users to a certain extent. Chapters 5 and 6 of the Commercial Bank Law of China focus on the content of the public disclosure system. The basic legal framework has been gradually improved with development, but under the premise of public disclosure of information, effective supervision is still very

limited. First of all, the accounting system is the fundamental source of information. Public accounting statements are the main source of information generally available to the domestic banking industry. In view of the fact that the current overall accounting system is still in the process of continuous reform, there are inevitably loopholes in the supervision of commercial banks. At the same time, the regulatory mechanism needs to be further improved. China's Commercial Bank Law lacks a clear position on the overall structure and process of the system of public disclosure of information, resulting in its failure to form a good system. At the same time, some acts of failure to perform their duties are constantly emerging, which is difficult to really avoid. Therefore, we can further promote the optimization of the overall system by improving the punishment to curb the disclosure of major false information by relevant responsible persons and ensuring the effective implementation of standardized behaviors.

Lack of support and guidance from relevant policies

Commercial banks constitute the main body of China's financial market, which has a great impact on the economy and society. China has constantly introduced relevant policies and measures to regulate and guide the development of commercial banks. However, few policies can provide necessary support and guidance to the financial risk management of commercial banks, which makes China's commercial banks have strong limitations in the process of implementing financial risk management. They can only proceed from their own internal management perspective without fully considering the relevant needs for the development of the entire financial market. The financial risk management measures and related mechanisms adopted by the bank will not only endanger its own development but also threaten the development of the entire financial market in China once problems occur. The important reason is that the relevant government departments do not pay enough attention to the financial risk management of commercial banks. At the same time, due to the large number of commercial banks in China, their development is different, and there is a large gap in the demand for financial risk management. Therefore, our government has great difficulties in formulating and implementing relevant policies.

Countermeasures and Suggestions for Strengthening Financial Risk Management of Commercial Banks

Improvement and optimization of financial risk management measures

For commercial banks, if they want to improve their financial risk management ability, they must first improve and optimize financial risk management measures. On the one hand, managers should pay more attention to financial risk management, take it as an important basis for commercial banks to implement comprehensive risk management, constantly strengthen the application of financial risk management methods and skills in practical work, and invest necessary resources to innovate in all aspects, innovate their financial risk management measures according to the development needs of commercial banks and even the financial market, reduce the cost of financial risk management, and improve the efficiency of risk management. On the other hand, in the process of implementing financial risk management, commercial banks should not only set out from the perspective of their own development but also establish a strategic vision of global development. They should constantly learn from the advanced experience and measures of other large commercial banks and make effective improvements to enable them to fully meet the needs of financial risk management of commercial banks, so as to promote the development of commercial banks.

We will strengthen the compensation incentive mechanism for financial management personnel. A fair and reasonable salary mechanism is conducive to the employees' better subjective initiative in their work. In commercial banks, it is understandable that the compensation mechanism is biased towards business departments. The problem of a large income gap between employees of different business lines

does exist. Therefore, providing employees with a more reasonable and fair compensation mechanism can make employees more hopeful and enthusiastic about their work. At the same time, a fair and reasonable reward and punishment system is more likely to encourage outstanding employees to move forward, prevent some employees who violate professional ethics from continuing to sink, and further improve the professional ethics of the overall employees of commercial banks.

Establishing an excellent humanistic environment to enrich financial risk management is also essential. Excellent commercial banks will certainly emphasize their own business culture, establish a “people-oriented” business culture, greatly strengthen the sense of belonging of employees, and further strengthen the cultural characteristics of commercial banks. Respecting the legitimate needs of employees at the psychological level from a practical point of view can often enable employees to exhibit stronger work enthusiasm in their work. Creating a harmonious working environment is conducive to relieving the huge working pressure on commercial bank employees. A flexible working system for financial risk management practitioners can not only ease the psychological pressure caused by tedious financial risk management work but also reduce the negative emotions caused by long-term fixed jobs. The development of financial risk management depends on the strength of the team. In a good working environment, the understanding between superiors and subordinates and the cooperation between colleagues can create a stable and sustainable operation of a financial risk management mechanism. Sub-branch J can achieve a better balance between enriching the work motivation of old employees and promoting the growth of new employees, so as to promote the progress of the overall financial risk management team.

Cultivation and introduction of professional financial risk management talents

First, commercial banks should pay full attention to the importance of professional talents to improve their financial risk management and conduct all-round training for their existing financial risk management personnel in the actual management and development process so that they can master advanced financial risk management concepts and methods and achieve the innovation of financial risk management mode of commercial banks through the promotion of professional talents, to lay a strong talent pool for financial risk management and all aspects of the development of commercial banks, so as to enhance their risk management ability and realize their healthy and long-term development. Secondly, commercial banks should introduce a group of professional financial risk management talents from outside through a sound human resource management mechanism so that they can inject fresh blood into the current financial risk management team of commercial banks in China, constantly optimize the talent structure, always maintain the construction of excellent talent teams, and promote commercial banks to have the guarantee of professional talents in the process of financial risk management.

1. Strictly implement the internal control system. The internal control culture is a part of the current commercial bank culture, which should form a certain cultural system to make it have an appeal and then promote its execution. When implementing the internal control system, we must ensure the seriousness of the system itself and ensure that system inspection and accountability are not mere formalities, which precisely determine whether the internal control system can operate effectively.

First of all, the inspectors of the internal control system should be given comprehensive supervision and inspection rights, independent of the business operators. Secondly, the frequency of internal control inspections should not be completely fixed. Irregular spot checks can help inspectors find deeper problems. Thirdly, complete and clear inspection standards are indispensable as the basis for determining the inspection content. Implementing specific inspection standards into business implementation standards is more conducive to the development of the overall business of commercial banks.

2. The internal control system should be predictive. The establishment and implementation of the system do not mean blindly sticking to the rules. The system also needs to keep pace with the times, constantly adapt to the development of the internal and external environment, and also adapt to the overall

business environment and management strategy. The development and change of the internal control system should include the prediction of the overall operation and development direction of commercial banks and should not simply apply the existing historical experience or a special case. In order to make the internal control system predictable, we must pay attention to the link between formulating the system initially, maintaining the design idea of financial risk prediction, and integrating the financial risk prediction into all aspects of the business. In the process of implementation and operation of the system, problems are found, solved, predicted, and constantly improved.

3. The internal control system should be improved in a timely manner. The internal control system with predictability can find potential or potential risk problems, but if it is not improved over time, the predictability will lose its inherent significance. The characteristics of the financial industry environment determine that the business environment of commercial banks is changing with each passing day and cannot remain unchanged or develop slowly. On the basis of the development characteristics of the international financial industry and in combination with China's national conditions, its commercial banks should improve their internal control system in real time to ensure that the institutional changes keep up with the trend of the times.

4. The internal control system should be prudent. With the gradual development of China's financial reform, the entry threshold of the banking industry is relatively open, which has led to the influx of a large amount of private capital into the banking industry in recent years. The rapid growth of commercial banks has also brought about a large number of operational problems. Small commercial banks continue to expose a variety of financial risks, prompting the regulatory authorities to continuously strengthen supervision, regardless of changes in the overall regulatory policy of the industry. The system is not perfect. With the development of the times and the change in supervision orientation, there will always be backwardness and defects. While commercial banks are constantly improving their internal control systems, they should examine the links in their internal systems that are not in line with the times and are difficult to change. The system should be viewed with prudence and should not be formulated and implemented solely for the sake of the system.

5. The internal control system requires information disclosure and strengthening communication. Internal information disclosure and efficient communication at all links are necessary ways to ensure the effective operation of the internal control system. With reference to the information disclosure mechanism of commercial banks in China, commercial banks should standardize and improve the information disclosure system and workflow and accurately, timely, completely, and truly disclose all major information about their business development in accordance with relevant regulations. Through cooperation with the increasingly developed media network, the reasonable and compliant disclosure of the commercial banks' own operating conditions is more conducive to the improvement of their social reputation and better safeguards the interests of all parties.

Improvement of support and guidance of relevant policies

From the perspective of the development of commercial banks and the current financial market, relevant government departments should effectively analyze their risk management, formulate and implement effective financial risk management measures, provide necessary guidance for the actual financial risk management of commercial banks, regulate their management measures in the form of relevant laws and regulations, and avoid large deviations in the financial risk management process of commercial banks in order to ensure the healthy and orderly development of China's entire financial market. On the other hand, it is necessary to effectively subdivide different types of commercial banks according to their development status, formulate relevant guidance mechanisms according to different situations, and ensure that various government management measures can be effectively applied in the financial risk management of commercial banks through strict supervision and management measures.

Strengthening the support and guidance of relevant government policies is a necessary measure for the financial risk management of commercial banks, which should be given full attention. Commercial banks in order to ensure the healthy and orderly development of China's entire financial market.

The financial risk management of commercial banks is an important part of their business development, and the overall management content and method play a vital role in their steady development. In the whole process of writing this paper, first of all, based on a variety of related theoretical research, it specifically discusses the connotation of financial risk. Then further combine the current operation mode and status, set relevant financial risk evaluation indicators, and analyze the current financial risks. Then, combined with the score results of relevant indicators, it specifically discusses the causes of financial risk at the J Sub branch.

Finally, the relevant improvement measures are proposed. The conclusions of this paper are as follows:

1. There are two main problems in the financial risk management of commercial banks. The first is the decrease in asset liquidity and the increase in debt ratio. Second, non-performing loans caused a decline in the overall asset quality.
2. The causes of financial risk management problems in commercial banks are divided into external and internal causes. The external causes are the influence of regulatory authorities and the influence of financing methods. The internal factors are the rising liquidity ratio, the slow turnover of assets, the need to further improve financial information management, the insufficient construction of internal control, the need to improve, the insufficient level of intermediate business, the weak sense of risk, the lack of awareness of importance, and the unbalanced quality of employees.
3. Suggestions for improving the financial risk management of commercial banks include: first, strengthening liquidity management and grasping risk assessment; second, improving asset security and loan structure; third, developing diversified operations; and fourth, strengthening the construction of the banking industry.
4. The institutional countermeasures to strengthen the financial risk management of commercial banks are as follows: first, optimize the internal control system and improve self-management; second, promote the financial risk early warning system and enhance security needs.

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